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ABERRANT CHAETOTAXY IN THE SPECIES OF TERELLIINI (DIPTERA: TEPHRITIDAE)

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Korneyev, V. A. & Troshyn, A.M. Aberrant chaetotaxy in the species of Terelliini (Diptera: Tephritidae). — Specimens of *Orellia falcata* and *Chaetorellia jaceae* with aberration in the number and position of dorsocentral setae are recorded from Ukraine.

Key words. Diptera, Tephritidae, chaetotaxy, aberration.

Корнейєв, В. О. і Трошин, А.М. Аберантна хетотаксія видів Terelliini (Diptera: Tephritidae). — Зареєстровано відхилення від норми в кількості і положенні дорсоцентральної щетинок у *Orellia falcata* і *Chaetorellia jaceae*.

Ключові слова. Diptera, Tephritidae, хетотаксія, аберация.

Introduction

The tribe Terelliini includes about 90 species widespread mainly in the Palaearctic Region, with a few species occurring also in the Afrotropical, Nearctic and Oriental Regions (Norrbom et al. 1999, and more recent additions). Larvae of these flies infest mainly flower heads of asteraceous plants of the tribes Cardueae, Cichorieae, and Vernonieae.

Chaetotaxy and pattern of mesonotum were proposed by Hendel (1927) to separate the genera *Chaetorellia* Hendel, *Chaetostomella* Hendel, *Terellia* Robineau-Desvoidy and *Orellia* Robineau-Desvoidy currently assigned to the tribe Terelliini: all the species with the presutural dorsocentral seta (Fig. 3) were attributed to *Chaetorellia*, whereas those without presutural dorsocentrals were assigned to the other three genera. Korneyev (1986) rearranged species based on morphology of the phallus, which is a complex character specific for subgenera or groups of species and sometimes non-correlating to external characters such as details of body vestiture, wing, thorax or abdomen dark patterns.

Chaetotaxy uncommon for *Terellia* and *Chaetostomella* (well developed presutural dorsocentral seta) was

described also for *Terellia blanda* (Richter, 1975) and *Chaetostomella baezi* Merz, 2000, but no exclusions were known either for *Orellia* or for *Chaetorellia*.

The genus *Orellia* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830 is represented by 4 species restricted in their distribution to the Palaearctic Region (see Korneyev, 2003). They differ from the other species of the tribe Terelliini by having bulged phallus glans with short filaments of the acrophallus, long posteroapical lobe of the cell cua (= cup) and 10 shining black spots, one pair of which lies directly on the transverse suture and bears no setae (Fig. 1). They are associated with the asteraceous plants of the tribe Cichorieae: *Podospermum*, *Scorzonera*, *Tragopogon* and, rarely, *Taraxacum* (Korneyev, 1987).

The rest of Terelliini except *Terellia tarbinskiorum* group of species have very short lobe of cup and black spots only at the bases of setae. Presence of presutural dorsocentral setae is a diagnostic character of the genus *Chaetorellia* Hendel, which includes 9 species associated with different *Centaurea* s. l. host plants.

Detailed examination of the collection material during preparation of a monograph of Ukrainian Tephritidae revealed examples of aberrant chaetotaxy and mesonotum pattern also in the two latter genera.

Results

Orellia falcata (Scopoli, 1763) (Figs 1, 3)

Material. Ukraine: Zaporizhzhya Region: Altahir, nr Bohatyr vill. [46.63N, 35.28E], 5–6.06.2008, 1 ♂ (Yu. Verves) (SIZK).

This is a common species widespread from Western Europe to Central Asia infesting stems of various species of

Tragopogon. The male (Fig. 3) has an additional presutural pair of dorsocentral setae and an extra postsutural dorsocentral seta on the left side of mesonotum hitherto not described for *Orellia* species.

Chaetorellia jaceae (Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830) (Figs 2, 4–5)

Material. Ukraine: Kyiv Region: Mryhi, [50.26N, 30.57E], 26.06.2006, 1 ♂ (E. Kameneva), Khodosiivka, [50.23N, 30.53E], 18.07.2009, 1 ♂ (S. Korneyev) (SIZK).

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Figs 1–3. *Orellia falcata* (1,3) and *Chaetorellia jaceae* (2): 1, 2 — normal chaetotaxy and dark pattern of mesonotum; 3 — habitus, dorsal view, showing aberrant chaetotaxy and dark pattern of mesonotum (arrows show supernumerary setae and dark spots).

Figs. 4–5. *Chaetorellia jaceae*: aberrant chaetotaxy and dark pattern of the mesonotum (arrows show the absent setae and dark spots).

This is a common species widespread from Western Europe to Central Asia infesting flower heads of *Centaurea jacea* and *C. nigra*. The males on Figs 4–5 have an aberration of chaetotaxy hitherto not described for *Chaetorellia* species: one presutural or one postsutural dorsocentral seta are lacking only on the right side of mesonotum.

Discussion

Number and arrangement of setae (the chaetotaxy) is considered to be a complex of important and constant diagnostic characters of Tephritoidea, but in some cases, aberrations in these characters happen. They are known to be common, for instance, in *Dorycera* (Ulidiidae) and *Oedaspis* (Tephritidae), but are described here in Terelliini for the first time showing that monothetic identification key characters are to be used with caution.

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